

A SOCIO-PRAGMATIC RELEVANCE OF TRADITIONAL MUSICAL INSTRUMENTS IN EJAGHAM CULTURE

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the socio-cultural relevance of traditional musical instruments in Ejagham culture, describes the types of traditional musical instruments in Ejagham society, investigates the role of traditional musical instruments in Ejagham culture as well as determine new trend in the use of traditional musical instruments in Ejagham culture. The traditional musical instruments in Ejagham society mirror the deep cultural heritage of the people. They are use for diverse purposes in Ejagham cultural setting and play a crucial role in many cultural activities especially, Communication. The study hinged on the indigenous knowledge systems theory for its analysis and also adopted the qualitative research design using the semi-structured interview to gather data during field work. The finding of the study reveals that Ejagham society has a variety of traditional musical instruments that reflect its unique cultural heritage. Also, the carving and playing of the traditional musical instruments require a high level of skill, demonstrating the ingenuity of the people. Finding also shows that some traditional musical instruments are the inheritance of specific families which serve as the custodians of the skills of carving or playing them and in turn hand down this knowledge from one generation to another. The finding also indicates that these instruments play a crucial role in the cultural activities of the people as a means of entertainment and tools for communicating cultural nuance, a cultural role that is being eroded due to global force of change. This study hopes to stirrup and awakens the consciousness of Ejagham people on the need to make meaningful effort towards the preservation of the culture in face of global influence.

KEYWORDS: Ejagham, musical instruments, carving, playing, sculptor

Introduction

Traditional musical instruments are musical devices that produce sound by shaking, hitting rubbing, blowing, beating or plucking. They are classified under the following, aerophonic, chordophonic, idophonic and membranophonic instruments (Umezina, Ibekwe & Esimone, 2020). Aerophones are those instruments that produce sounds through the air columns in materials with natural or acquired bore such as horns, gourds and bamboos. Membranophones are musical instruments that produce sounds through a stretched animal membrane over a

wooden metal or casing. Chordophone are musical instruments that produce sounds through the vibration of a string or strings (Umezinwa, Ibekwe & Esimone, 2020).

Traditional musical instruments are part of the cultural life of a people as they facilitate many cultural activities. Keith (2022) believes musical instruments are central components of both the tangible and intangible cultural heritage. For instance, musical instruments play a crucial role in the lives of many Nigerians because singing and dancing accompanies the musical instruments at social festivities such as wedding and funeral (Cooper, 2012). This view aligns with IFRA-Nigeria (2023) that noted that traditional music in African culture takes place during purely social events such as naming ceremonies, funerals and coronation of a new king. This arguably reveals the social viability of music and musical instruments in an African society.

Music is described as a combination of vocal or instrumental sounds or tones in varying melody, harmony, rhythm and timbre to form structurally complete and emotionally expressive composition (Oziogu, 2011). Music is hardly complete without instruments because instrumental sound gives structure and life to vocal sound. It is this perfect harmony of the vocal and instrumental sound that makes music complete. Although, musical instruments are universal and cultural possessions, however, they differ from culture to culture as well as in the communicative role they play. It is on the basis of the idiosyncratic nature of musical instruments that Igbi (2019) noted that African societies have a plethora of musical instruments ranging from skin drums, flutes, woodblock, ritual rattle, rattle and many others. Traditional musical instruments are made from different materials such as wood, animal skin and horns. The ability of the instrument to produce a unique sound is tied to the special skill of the carver and the player.

Apart from the predominant role of music, traditional musical instruments are use for communication. They are use to communicate cultural nuances of a people in different socio-cultural contexts and convey unique messages that are interpreted within the culture in which the instruments are used. This in many cases, when they are played or blown, tell the story of the people; their pains, struggles, victories, hopes and aspiration and their history. This means that traditional musical instruments vary from culture to culture and the cultural nuances they communicate also vary from culture to culture. Okpara (2016) is of the view that every culture has her musical instruments which she is identified and in spite of acculturation, industrialization and westernization, there is still an inner craving for in every culture for her cultural posterity. However, this assertion is not absolutely true because many societies are fast losing their cultural wealth to wind of social, political, environmental and cultural change.

Although Okpara (2016) further noted that there is a general consensus among scholars that traditional instruments are fast disappearing and effort should be made to preserve them. In spite gradual loss of indigenous cultural knowledge, traditional musical instruments tell a lot about the culture in which they are produce and use. This supports the opinion of Awoonor (1975) who asserts that history does not only exist in written records and books but also in non-documentary sources such as oral traditions, the findings of archeology, ethnology and musicology. He went on to say that the sum total of a people's way of life coherently developed in their material and spiritual cultures, in the tools and implements, in their institutions and concepts of God and many concepts that exist in an order that can be clarified through names. This history of a people can also be clarified not only through names either personal names or place names as remonstrated by (Ansa & Okon, 2004), but also through traditional musical instruments which give unique cultural identity to a specific ethnic group and Ejagham ethnic group in particular.

Ejagham has a rich cultural heritage that is manifested in many areas of their existence and one of such areas is in their cultural instruments. Traditional musical instruments in Ejagham society is a combination of the skills of the carver who possesses the cultural knowledge to play the instrument to provide the sound that appeals to the listener and the skill of the player who has the cultural skill to communicate the cultural nuance through the instrument. In Ejagham society, traditional instruments are part of the social activities of the people. They are used in different varieties of cultural festivals because many cultural activities in Ejagham society are accompanied by music in which traditional musical instrument play a crucial role. However, traditional musical instruments are not use for music purposes alone, but also communicate information and pass messages that reveal specific happenings within the communities. This means that traditional musical instruments are type of traditional media that can communicate different types of messages through the way they sound or played. Traditional musical instruments are fast losing their socio-cultural significance in modern times in Ejagham society due to forces of change attributed to modernization, westernization and globalization. These factors combined, have reduced most indigenous cultural practices significantly or have encouraged their devaluation in one form or the other.

However, many traditional musical instruments are hardly used in many cultural events and activities and are gradually being replaced by modern devices. Due to their infrequent use, they are fast becoming obsolete and it is manifested in loss of the skills to produce and play them effectively by the younger generation. The production and playing of some traditional musical instruments require special skills that is acquired through informal education and preserved through continuous practice. In some instances, the knowledge is usually handed by the older generation to the younger generation. In many cases, this skills and knowledge is a family possession that should be preserved through time. However, when there is gap in this transmission of knowledge and the constant use of the traditional instrument, it leads to the loss of the cultural knowledge. This study therefore aimed at investigating Ejagham traditional musical instruments in a bit to gain insight into their socio-pragmatic relevance in Ejagham culture.

1.1.1 The Ejagham people

In an attempt to carry out discussion on Ejagham traditional musical instruments, effort is made to provide a brief historical background of the speakers of the language. Onor(1994) observed that the term "Ejagham" is derived from "Ijagham" a sacred lake believed to be the cradle of Ejagham people. "Ijagham" is located within Ejagham territory in the present day Republic of Cameroun. Onor (1994) revealed that Ayuk, an Essayist, has also attempted to account for how the terminology "Ijagham" evolved. According to him, many oral traditions point to the fact that the name "Ijagham" must have been coined from the word "Ejak" which means let's clap. This was probably uttered by the first ancestors of Ejagham people when they first saw the extraordinary piece of water. At present, the Ejagham ethnic group is one of the major ethnic groups in Cross River State, Nigerian and occupies a contiguous area scattering across eight Local Government Areas of Cross River State, Nigeria and the South Western Region of the Republic of Cameroun.

The term Ejagham is used in reference to several groups which include Qua of Calabar, Odukpani, Akamkpa and Akpabuyo (block 1), Etung, Ofutop, Akparabong, Nde, Nselle, Nnam, Nkome, Olulumo, Balep (block 2) while Nkim, Nkum, and Ekajuk of Bakor make up (block 3). The different Ejagham sub-groups are found in Etung, Ikom, Calabar Municipality, Akamkpa, Odukpani, Akpabuyo and Ogoja Local Government of Cross River State, Nigeria. Ejagham ethnic group has unique cultural practices that give them a unique cultural identity. These include the fattening room practice, *Mgbè society*, *Nkím*, *Aním Nsìbíri* and the *Ekpà*

women cult and the *Angbú*. Apart from the cultural practices of the Ejagham people, they occupy a rich fertile land and the savanna rain forest which make their primary occupation farming and hunting. Few Ejagham people live in cities, the rest predominantly live in the rural areas. This account for why farming is their primary occupation.

The cultural practices of the people include *mgbè* (leopard). It is a secret society that has played both a legislative and executive role in Ejagham society. Initiated into the *mgbe* society are males. Although oral tradition has it that the *mgbe* society was a discovery of the women but were manipulated out of it by the men who later become the custodians of the society. It is only in rare cases that a woman is an initiate of the society. The mode of communication among the initiates is through signs, symbols and the *nsibiri* and incantations. The *mgbè* secret society of the Ejagham is a very revered institution and the most important creation of the people that depict the virtues of the leopard (*mgbè*), an animal which exhibit enormous strength, dignity, and valour. The *mgbè* society still remains one of the Ejagham cultural institutions used in maintaining law and order in the society.

2.1 Previous studies

Umezina, Ibekwe & Esimone (2020) examine the Igbo music from the perspective of organology, the study of musical instruments with focus on classification. The study indicates that igbo people are music-loving and music making people and in creating their own music, have invented for themselves a wide-range of musical instruments. These instruments are made from living and non-living creatures in a very broad division. The material elements that are used in making musical instruments include wood, metal, or iron, clay, hides and skin, gourds, bamboo, ropes, animal horns and seeds. Igbo musical instruments fall within the following broad categories- idiophones (*mgbeleke*, *alo*), membranophones (*igba, nkwa*), Aerophones (*oja*) and Chordophone (*une*).

Okpara (2016) study gave insight into some of the Nigerian musical instruments, their classifications, functions, mode of construction as well as their relevance as means of communication. The study findings show that many indigenous Nigerian musical instruments communicate in languages which the performers or dancers understand. This is to say that indigenous musical instruments such as the *aja* (Igbo flute) and *iya-ilu* (Yoruba talking drum) speak in non verbal languages which only the performer understand. Findings show further that musical instrument such as *aja* and *iya ilu* sing praises to heroes and great achievers in the community which are clearly understood by the recipients.

Micah (2019) investigated indigenous system in traditional musical instruments with focus on production and development. The study established the link between traditional musical instruments and the sculpture as a depository of indigenous knowledge systems in music. The study maintains that traditional musical instruments have been handed down from generation to generation and over the years the sculptors have played a vital role in the making of musical instrument. This is because for someone to be able to make a musical instrument, the person needs to have an idea about the material and characteristics.

Abiodun (2023) study conceptually and theoretically advocated for technological innovation of Agidigbo traditional musical instrument. The study revealed the different types of Agidigbo traditional musical instrument which range from the smallest (soprano), medium size (alto or tenor) and the large (bass). The Agidigbo had four sides, a pair each of the same length and breadth, which made it a rectangular-like box. The study also showed that Agidigbo has soundboard with a perforated sound hole, and a base. The study advocate for the preservation of materials for Agidigbo musical instrument to be assessed before application to evaluate their

impact on sound as they may significantly affect the acoustic properties of the musical instruments and thus alter both their tangible and intangible identity.

Rehman & Chaudhry (2017) work focuses on the cultural perception of arts and different importance and values of instruments and performance. The study revealed that the art of making of a musical instrument, playing it and to move or dance to that instrument is duly considered to be an abhorrent act in Pakistan. This suggests that the use of musical instruments in Pakistan is going to be extinct overtime. The study noted that musical instruments are source of bread and butter for artists and performers as their lives are connected with this instruments. The study recommended that the government and art institutions in the country can play a pivotal role in saving and preserving the instruments and the artists' classical culture.

In light of this review, incredible insight has been gained into the different cultural contexts and scholarly perspectives in which different scholars have approached the study of traditional musical instruments. Their findings have provided this study with unique understanding about traditional musical instruments. However, none of the scholars looked at traditional musical instruments within the socio-cultural context of the Ejagham society. This study therefore aimed to fill this research gap.

2.1 Theoretical framework

This study hinged on the indigenous knowledge systems theory (IKS) which emerges in the late 20th century as a collective interdisciplinary scholarship inspired by the work of scholars like Paul Sillotte, Ngugi Wa Thiongo among other scholars. It gain recognition around the 1980s and 1990s. a varieties of scholars such as Smith(1999), Battiste (2005), Deloria (1969) and Cajette (1999) have made significant contributions to the theory of indigenous system theory. The theory draws from array of academic traditions and cultural practices. The theory offers insight into how indigenous people create, use and transmit musical knowledge that is rooted in their specific cultural and environmental contexts.

This theory believes that in many indigenous cultures' music is not separated from their social life and integrated into the Cosmology, rituals, healing, education and governance. Traditional instrument like drums, flutes, rattles are often secret tools that play crucial role in music making and for entertainment. However, traditional musical instruments are not just tools for entertainment but are means of communication. That is, the sounds produce by these instruments are believed to communicate with ancestors, spirit or the land and are seen as living entities with their own spiritual force. The knowledge of music and musical instruments is often passed down orally or experientially through apprenticeship and ceremonial participation. Again, the theory avers the ecological and spiritual significance of traditional instrument. In other word, many traditional musical instrument are made from locally source materials with knowledge of those materials part of its marking process.

The theory believes that the making and playing of traditional instruments often involve a deep understanding of materials, craftsmanship, a musical skills passed down through generations, forming a unique indigenous knowledge system. It emphasizes the importance of preserving knowledge instruments are not just tools for creating music, but also carriers of history, ritual, and artistic expression. This theory has been applied in many cultural studies and by UNESCO and suits the study on traditional musical instruments in Ejagham culture.

3.1 Research methodology

This research adopted the qualitative ethnographic research design. This design allows the researcher to collect data through direct observations, interviews, focus group discussions and naturally occurring data (Singh, 2023). The geographic area covered in the study is the Etung Local Government Area of Cross River State. Etung Local Government holds a very unique feature as a homogenous Local government of Ejagham people and has rural community setting. A total of 15 participants who are conversant with the knowledge about musical instruments in three communities, 9 men, 6 women, 3 traditional chiefs, 3 cultural groups and 3 family heads and 3 members of three cultural groups make up the participants. The data was collected directly from the participants during field investigation through the oral interview and informal interactions during social gatherings. The study adopted the descriptive method of data analysis.

4.0 Data presentation

4.1 Ejagham traditional musical instruments

Traditional musical instruments are found across culture and society, although they are unique and differ across societies. The Ejagham society as one of Africa's traditional societies has its own traditional musical instruments that reflect unique cultural heritage of the people. Ejagham traditional musical instruments are categorized under the following:

(a) Membranophone

This refers to instruments that are made from the stretched membrane of animal on a holed wood. Example of this type of traditional musical instrument is the skin drums. According to Microsoft Encarta (2007):

“Drums are classified as membranophones because their sound is produced by vibrating a membrane. It consists of a skin tied over the top and pierced by a stick. Examples are Congo drum, talking drum, tambourine etc, conga drum is a long, narrow drum small frame drum played with the palm of the hand and fingers. Tambourine is a small frame drum that is constructed of a single membrane stretched over a circular rim, which usually has metal jingle disks attached to it. It can be played in three different ways: tapping the membrane with fingers, shaking the instrument of striking it against the body.”(p. 30,).

Drums are very common traditional musical instruments in Ejagham Culture. Music in during cultural ceremonies and activities are usually accompanied with the playing of drums. They come in different sizes and produce different sounds that are blended into a unique cultural music. However, three *okám* (drums) are prominent in Ejagham culture and fall under the following categories

- i. . *Ndàbá ndip* (long bottom). It has a longer dimension and produces a sound deeper and equates the base tone in modern musical instrument. Its sound is fixed depending on the kind of song that is sung.
- ii. *nchìmá ndip*(short buttocks). its size falls in between the first and the last categories. Its sound gives support to the first drum. A blend of the sounds of the first drum and the second drum keeps the music synchronized and danceable even when the talking drum is not talking.

- iii. *èkpìrà*(talking drum). It is the smallest drum among categories of Ejagham drums. It is use to facilitate communication between the dancers and singers. It is often played by highly skilled player who dictates the tempo of the dance and the dance steps of the dancers. These three types of drums are very important because they can produce any type of cultural music. They serve as a complete set. This does not mean other drums are not important.

(b) Aerophones

These are instruments played by blowing air into them. They produce sounds by the vibration of the air column. In Ejagham culture *òfìrìkó* (traditional flute) and *ìbáng* (animal horn) are examples of aerophones. The traditional flute in Ejagham culture is more of a communication instrument than music making instrument. It is used among the Ejagham people to communicate events such as sorrowful, fearful or attack. In many instances it is used to call warriors from their rest to prepare for action. It is played by a very skilled individual who can communicate the cultural nuances of the people in a way that it can be clearly understood by others.

(c) Idiophones

Idiophones are traditional musical instruments that produce sounds by the vibration of the entire body (Nwafor, 2010). They are played by hitting or shaking. According to ((Umezinwa, Ibekwe & Esimone, 2020) they include pot drum, slit wooden drum, bells, wooden gong (struck idiophones) and, rattle (shaken idiophones). The idiophones in Ejagham culture include:

- i. *èyúk* (wooden gong). It is a musical instrument that is carved or produced from a large tree trunk. The production of the wooden gong requires skilled traditional sculptor who have knowledge of the wood, and excavation of the interior of the trunk to produce sound it is intended to. The production of this musical instrument usually takes months and often time done in secrecy.
- ii. *ìtókòró* (small wooden drum).The wooden drum is an Ejagham traditional musical instrument that accompanies the drums during music making and mostly used during masquerade dance. This means that some instruments fit into specific socio-cultural activity than others. The wrong musical instrument in some way alters the music and effect it is intended to create. The wooden drum produced powerful effect and it is the most reason it is used during masquerade dance.
- iii. *àkàchák* (rattle) it is made up of raffia enclosed with beads. It is shaken to produce sound and it is used by traditional drummers or players to add melody to music. It always combines with drums to produce music. There is also another type of rattle that is made from bough with round balls made of wood attached at two holed end of the bough. The balls hit against each other when it is shaken to produc a sound. However, this is not use for music but by a traditional poet who communicate to people through wise cultural saying. The shaking is accompanied by deep philosophical sayings such as *oyák* Ejagham, *òtúk* Ejagham (you eat Ejagham, but abuse Ejagham). This is a philosophical saying in Ejagham society that interrogates into human relationships. In order word, you can be destroyed or harm by the same people eating fat from your resources.
- iv. *òkánkáng*(metal) it is made of metal and struck with stick to produce sound. It is used in music but mostly used for communication. It is mostly used as a tool to summon especially age grade members to their gathering.
- v. *Ekùfúng/èbúk* (metal gong) it is long in dimension also struck with a stick to produce sound. Among the Ejagham people, the instrument serves as strong legislative tool by

the women. It is used by the female town crier to convey message of importance to the community. It also a means through which women are summoned to their gathering.

4.2 Discussion

The discussion revolves around the research questions raised earlier in this study. Based on the evidence presented in the data collected, three broad categories of musical instruments are found in Ejagham culture which include *èkùfúng/èbúk*, *òkángkáng*, *àkáchàk*, *itókòró* and *èyúk* (idiophones), *òfírìkó* and *ìbáng*(Aerophones), *òkám*(membranophone). The traditional musical instruments in Ejagham culture aligns with Igbi (2019) who noted that African societies have a plethora of musical instruments ranging from skin drums, flutes. woodblock, ritual rattle, rattle and many others. Traditional musical instruments are made from different materials such as wood, animal skin and horns. Also, Okpara (2016) noted that every culture has her musical instruments which she is known and identified with. These traditional musical instruments are used in different varieties of music. Although they are all musical instruments, some instruments are used in specific music, while others are used in all varieties of music. Again, traditional musical instruments play a crucial role in the social life of the people because they are used to produce traditional music in a variety of cultural events and activities in Ejagham society. This agrees with the indigenous knowledge system theory that asserts that traditional musical instruments play crucial roles in the social life of a society. Music is at the heart of every African society social life. Music is the purest spiritual essence, a part of a person's social and spiritual being; a vehicle for healing mind, body, and spirit and inseparable from life experience (Micah, 2019). It is evidence from the data presented that some instruments play dual role in Ejagham culture. They are used for entertainment as well as for communication purpose. They are means through which cultural nuance are expressed as their sounds tell a story about the people. They are used to reveal cultural events such as the death of prominent figures in the land, summon warriors to battle, call age grade members, celebration and other cultural issues. Hence, when they are played or struck, the effect of the sound is nuanced by the social situation of the community.

However, many changes are gradually taking place, impacting Ejagham traditional musical instruments in terms of their use and production. New modern music is gradually fused into many cultural activities and events. The playing and production of some traditional musical instruments is gradually fading away and this shift is coming on the heel of certain socio-cultural factors. There is lack of a systematic means of knowledge and skill transfer from one generation to another. Apart from the gap in Knowledge transfer, most of the activities surrounding the gathering of materials use in the production of some traditional musical instruments and the actual production have spiritual implication and done under concealment. This have a far reaching implication for the acquisition of this skills by younger generation who are not comfortable going through some of the rituals. Example of such Ejagham musical instruments are the wooden gong and the wooden drum which said to be produced in the night

In the same vein, the skills involved in the production and playing of some musical instruments is hereditary. In other word, it is that heritage of a specific family who in turn will carefully determine who should be entrusted with the sacred about the instruments when the older custodian of the sacret is about to die. Hence, the longevity of the skills and knowledge about musical instruments is dependent on the ability of the family to transmit the knowledge from one generation to another. This is because it is the collective knowledge of the player and carver that will assist in keeping the culture of traditional musical instruments alive in any given society. This also supports the claim of Flintoff (2004) who noted that while most instruments have obvious family origins, others are created by a union of the families of the

gods. This understanding helps give insight into the values that are placed on the instruments, the music and the materials they are created from (Micah,2019).

5.1 Conclusion

This paper explores the socio-pragmatic relevance of traditional musical instrument in Ejagham culture. Traditional musical instruments are cultural possessions that play a key role in the cultural music industry of many African societies. They are part of the social life of a people as they are used to produce music which is at the heart of many social activities and ceremonies. However, traditional musical instruments though exist across culture; they differ from culture to culture. In other word, the materials and production reflect the specificity of a given culture and society. Based on the above, the Ejagham society has its own musical instrument used in creating music in a variety of social activities. The findings revealed that apart from the entertainments, some traditional musical instruments are media of communication. They are used to communicate specific cultural nuances. It also showed that the playing and production of some musical instruments is gradually dwindling in the phase of western and global influences.

5.2 Recommendations

In light of the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- (a) The need for a robust informal education system where many cultural skills and knowledge can be communicated should be established as part of the measure in sustaining cultural knowledge. This will help sustain and transmit the knowledge through a very systematic means.
- (b) Cultural centered actions involving youth in heritage-related activities such as workshops, internships and cultural heritage programmes should be organized across Ejagham communities to educate them on the need to protect their cultural heritage.
- (c) Ejagham cultural organizations and bodies should strive to instill a sense of pride and responsibility in future generations through awareness and sensitization of the youth on the value of preserving cultural heritage.

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